

Darwinian Quantum Gravity obtains Gravitational Constant from Quantum Electrodynamics and Quantum Chromodynamics

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Abstract

The capacity for Darwinian Quantum Gravity (DQG) approach to quantum gravity to obtain the gravitational constant value for the contemporary universe, G_{exp} , directly from Quantum Electrodynamics (QED) and Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) parameters, implies that the gravitational constant G being equal to G_{exp} depends on the value of the typical diameter of the major matter constituents of the universe, which are the baryons. Therefore, since baryons only occur after baryon creation, the value of the gravitational constant is approximately equal to G_{exp} only after baryogenesis and during Cosmic Inflation. For the remaining periods before baryogenesis, the gravitational constant is considerably smaller than G_{exp} . The reduction of the gravitational constant allows for a reduction of DQG's physics-cell's time-step size and the corresponding increase in DQG's maximum pure-state mass.

1 Deduction

1.1 Einstein Field Equations as expressing energy density relations

The mostly, but not necessarily completely, symmetric spacetime metric tensor $\mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu}$ corresponds to a Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$. The Ricci tensor may also be obtained as expressing the distortion of 3-dimensional spheres of radius ξ_{sph} . Specifically, the Ricci tensor is proportional to ratio between the volume of such spheres in curved spacetime, endowed with the metric $\mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu}$ and subject to a distortion u^μ , the $V_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu}, u^\mu)$; and the volume of corresponding spheres in flat spacetime with Lorentz metric $\eta_{\mu\nu}$, the $V_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \eta_{\mu\nu})$. To extract the Ricci tensor from deformation of 3-dimensional spheres, it is introduced the definition

$$\mathfrak{D}V_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu}, u^\mu, \eta_{\mu\nu}) := V_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu}, u^\mu) - V_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \eta_{\mu\nu}) . \quad (1)$$

For a deformation vector u^μ centered on the sphere and characterized by the scale ξ_{sph} , the relevant ratio (Gray and Vanhecke, 1979; Wald, 1984) is

$$\frac{\mathfrak{D}V_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu}, u^\mu, \eta_{\mu\nu})}{V_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \eta_{\mu\nu})} \approx -\frac{1}{6\pi} R_{\mu\nu} u^\mu u^\nu . \quad (2)$$

For these 3-dimensional spheres of radius ξ_{sph} , let $\mathbf{A}_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu}, u^\mu)$ denote the area in curved spacetime and $\mathbf{A}_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \eta_{\mu\nu})$ the corresponding area in flat spacetime. Then, it is

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here defined the change in volume per unit area induced by a deformation displacement u^μ at scale ξ_{sph} as $\mathfrak{D}\mathbf{L}_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu}, \eta_{\mu\nu})_{\mu\nu}$, such that for any deformation displacement u^μ at scale ξ_{sph} , the corresponding volume alteration is

$$\mathfrak{D}V_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu}, u^\mu, \eta_{\mu\nu}) := \mathfrak{D}\mathbf{L}_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu}, \eta_{\mu\nu})_{\mu\nu} u^\mu u^\nu. \quad (3)$$

The tensor $\mathfrak{D}\mathbf{L}_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu}, \eta_{\mu\nu})_{\mu\nu}$ is therefore a covariant quantity preserved along geodesics. Consequently, general covariance constrains form of $\mathfrak{D}\mathbf{L}_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu}, \eta_{\mu\nu})_{\mu\nu}$ to be

$$\frac{\mathfrak{D}\mathbf{L}_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu}, \eta_{\mu\nu})_{\mu\nu}}{V_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \eta_{\mu\nu})} \approx -\frac{1}{6\pi} R_{\mu\nu}. \quad (4)$$

If energy content of the universe is concentrated in three-dimensional spheres, the Ricci tensor can be interpreted as resulting from the deformation of such spheres. This approach is motivated by the approximate sphericity of baryonic bound states, which dominate the rest-mass energy budget of ordinary matter. The Eq.(4) may therefore be inserted into the Einstein field equations (EFE). Let ρ_Λ denote the energy density associated with the cosmological constant Λ , and let $\tilde{T}_{\mu\nu}$ be the trace-reversed energy-momentum-stress tensor. Then the EFE, as given in Eq. 4.3.23 of Wald (1984), become

$$\tilde{T}_{\mu\nu} + \rho_\Lambda \mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu} \approx -\frac{3c^4}{4G} \frac{\mathfrak{D}\mathbf{L}_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu}, \eta_{\mu\nu})_{\mu\nu}}{V_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \eta_{\mu\nu})}. \quad (5)$$

Let $\langle \dots \rangle_{\{V\}}$ denote an average over a generic volume V . Consider now a volume $\mathfrak{V} \gg V_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \eta_{\mu\nu})$ with total energy $U_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}}$. Defining $\mathbf{A}_{\text{sph}} := \langle \mathbf{A}_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \eta_{\mu\nu}) \rangle_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}}$ and $V_{\text{sph}} := \langle V_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \eta_{\mu\nu}) \rangle_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}}$, then $\frac{V_{\text{sph}}}{A_{\text{sph}}} \approx \frac{4}{3} \xi_{\text{sph}}$. Further, it is here defined the unit-scale spherical-volume deformation tensor

$$\mathfrak{A}_{\mu\nu}^{\{\mathfrak{V}\}} := \left\langle \frac{\mathbf{A}_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \eta_{\mu\nu}) \mathfrak{D}\mathbf{L}_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu}, \eta_{\mu\nu})_{\mu\nu}}{V_{\text{sph}}(\xi_{\text{sph}}, \eta_{\mu\nu})} \right\rangle_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}}. \quad (6)$$

From Eq.(5), it then follows that

$$\tilde{T}_{\mu\nu} + \rho_\Lambda \mathfrak{g}_{\mu\nu} \approx -\frac{\xi_{\text{sph}} c^4}{V_{\text{sph}} G} \mathfrak{A}_{\mu\nu}^{\{\mathfrak{V}\}}. \quad (7)$$

The objective of relating Standard Model of Physics (SMP) quantum fields (QFs) energy density to G can be achieved by objectively determining the volume \mathfrak{V} with characteristic radius $\xi_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}} := \sqrt[3]{\frac{3\mathfrak{V}}{4\pi}}$, such that its energy density is

$$\frac{U_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}}}{\mathfrak{V}} = \frac{\xi_{\text{sph}} c^4}{V_{\text{sph}} G}. \quad (8)$$

1.2 Vacuum-state Energy Density

The identification of $\frac{U_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}}}{\mathfrak{V}} \mathfrak{A}_{\mu\nu}^{\{\mathfrak{V}\}}$ with ρ_0 is motivated not only by the physical interpretation of the two other terms, but also by the fact that the unit-scale tensor $\mathfrak{A}_{\mu\nu}^{\{\mathfrak{V}\}}$ encodes sphere-distortion dynamics at scale ξ_{sph} , averaged over a much larger scale $\xi_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}} \gg \xi_{\text{sph}}$. Therefore, for Eq.(8) to hold, one must have

$$\rho_0 := \frac{U_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}}}{\mathfrak{V}} = \frac{\xi_{\text{sph}} c^4}{V_{\text{sph}} G}. \quad (9)$$

The volume \mathfrak{V} vacuum-state energy density ρ_0 in Eq.(9) is proposed here to be associated with disconnected quantum loops, represented by disconnected Feynman diagrams.

Although such disconnected diagrams are formally associated with a spacetime hypervolume $V^{\{4\}}$ (Peskin and Schroeder, 1995), this association must be treated with care within SMP quantum field theory (QFT) as the internal coordinates $\{z_1, z_2, \dots\}$ of these hypervolumes are not connected to external points and therefore cannot be interpreted as physical spacetime coordinates in the usual sense. However, in Darwinian Quantum Gravity (DQG) (Lori, 2022), the de Broglie relation yields a maximum pure-state mass $m_{\text{thresh}} = 2\pi\hbar/(c\lambda_{\text{min}})$. Consequently, the Einstein equation implies a maximum total energy for a pure-state, $E_{\text{thresh}} = m_{\text{thresh}}c^2$. Within this framework, the coordinates $\{z_1, z_2, \dots\}$ of a disconnected quantum loop can be consistently interpreted as being associated with the spacetime volume of a finite set of particles that are entangled with the quantum loop as part of an entangled pure-state; with that entangled pure-state volume possibly including spacetime regions that are not causally connected in a classical way. The electron-positron pair creation permitted by the Heisenberg uncertainty principle through such disconnected quantum loops forms a "vacuum bubble" that has an electric dipole with a time-varying dipole moment $e \times d$; where e is the electron charge magnitude and d is the square root of mean squared separation between electron and positron. The total energy U of that dipole; assuming it has an average dipole density N and assuming both that no contribution from distances smaller than b can occur and that vacuum permittivity is ϵ_0 ; is obtained from Eq. 1.55 and Eq. 4.13 of Ref. Jackson (1999) to be:

$$U = \frac{1}{12\pi\epsilon_0} e^2 \frac{d^2}{b^3} N. \quad (10)$$

By assuming \mathfrak{V} is the volume of the electron-positron pair's creation and annihilation "vacuum bubble", then $d = \xi_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}}$, which in this approach means that \mathfrak{V} corresponds to an ellipsoidal region. Letting $V_b = \frac{4\pi}{3}b^3$ denote the volume of a sphere, the energy $U_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}}$ contained in \mathfrak{V} represents the vacuum-state energy density ρ_0 within a "vacuum bubble" of volume \mathfrak{V} , thus clarifying Eq.(9). Using Eqs.(8), (9) and (10) obtains

$$\frac{c^4}{G} \approx \frac{e^2}{\epsilon_0} \frac{\xi_{\text{sph}}^2}{\xi_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}} V_b} N. \quad (11)$$

Combining the definition of $\xi_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}}$ with the assumption that V_{sph} corresponds to a spherical volume implying that $N = \xi_{\text{sph}}^3/\xi_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}}^3$, and substituting this result into Eq.(11) yields

$$\frac{c^4}{G} \approx \frac{e^2}{\epsilon_0} \frac{\xi_{\text{sph}}^5}{\xi_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}}^4 V_b}. \quad (12)$$

1.3 Obtaining Minimum Scale Value from Gravitational Constant

The Compton wavelength of the electron is $l_c = \frac{2\pi\hbar}{m_e c} = 2.43 \times 10^{-12}$ [m], where m_e is the electron mass. According to Quantum Electrodynamics (QED), the maximum separation between an electron and a positron during spontaneous electron-positron pair creation is $\mathbf{d} := \frac{l_c}{4\pi}$ (Feynman, 1985; Peskin and Schroeder, 1995). The corresponding effective "radius" of the quantum loop of the electron-positron combined pair-creation and pair-destruction, is, therefore, $\xi_{ep} = \mathbf{d}/2$. The ellipsoidal "vacuum bubble" associated with such a quantum loop has a major axis of length \mathbf{d} , with the other two axes reduced by factors φ and ϑ , with respective lengths $\varphi \mathbf{d}$ and $\vartheta \mathbf{d}$.

In presence of strong electric fields, meaning such fields approach the Schwinger limit $\mathfrak{E}_S := \frac{m_e^2 c^3}{e\hbar}$, the vacuum becomes unstable and electron-positron pair production occurs via the Schwinger mechanism. The electric field \mathfrak{E}_{ep} generated by one charge of the "vacuum bubble" pair at the position of the pair's other charge is a strong electric field as it is only slightly below the Schwinger limit.

The distance between electron and positron in the electron-positron pair of the "vacuum bubble" is $d = \varphi \mathbf{d}$. By assuming that the 3-dimensional energy-volume scaling balances Coulomb energy with "vacuum bubble" energy and that $\varphi \approx \vartheta$; that definition of fine-structure constant is $\alpha := \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0\hbar c}$, which for low temperatures is $\alpha \approx 1/137$; and that both elements of the electron-positron pair are considered, then, $\varphi \approx 2\sqrt[3]{\mathfrak{E}_{ep}/\mathfrak{E}_S} \approx 2\alpha^{1/3} \approx 0.39$. By considering that $\varphi \approx \vartheta$, it is then obtained that $\xi_{\{\mathfrak{V}\}} = \xi_{ep} \varphi^{2/3}$, and $d = \varphi \mathbf{d}$. Therefore, using the Coulomb equation semiclassical approximation to QED, the electric field associated with the electron-positron pair is $\mathfrak{E}_{ep}(d) \approx \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{e}{d^2} \lesssim \mathfrak{E}_S$. Except for dark energy and dark matter, the largest fraction of matter in the universe is made of sphere-like baryons; thus, the relevant spherical radius is the average baryon radius, meaning the gravitational attraction-causing spherical radius is the average baryon radius; hence, $\xi_{\text{sph}} = \xi_{\text{baryon}} \approx [0.86 \pm 0.01] \times 10^{-15}$ [m]. In DQG, the physics-cel is a spherical volume with radius r_{PC} and volume V_{PC} , and so $V_b = V_{\text{PC}} := \frac{4}{3}\pi r_{\text{PC}}^3$ is spherical as required in Eqs.(10)-(12). Combining these three considerations and substituting them into Eq.(12), plus considering that each physics-cell volume has a time-step $t_{\text{PC}} = \frac{2r_{\text{PC}}}{c}$ during which it processes I_{PC} qubits of information, with $I_{\text{PC}} = I_{\text{SMP}}$ (Lori, 2022, 2025b) having been valid since the appearance of all SMP QFs where I_{SMP} is a constant (Lori, 2025a). Similarly, SMP Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) and experimental observations imply that baryons are spherical (Ji, 1997; Miller, 2011) and so $V_{\text{sph}} = V_{\text{baryon}}$ is spherical. From QED considerations, the "vacuum bubble" volume is $\mathfrak{V} = \frac{4\pi\varphi\vartheta}{3}\xi_{ep}^3 = \frac{\pi}{12}\alpha^{\frac{2}{3}}\left[\frac{\hbar}{m_e c}\right]^3$, with $\mathfrak{V} \gg V_{\text{baryon}}$, being consistent with the assumptions made above. Considering that DQG's physics-cell have a radius r_{PC} which is the minimum scale, it is therefore appropriate to consider that $b = r_{\text{PC}}$. Combining these three identifications; respectively for ξ_{sph} , b and \mathfrak{V} ; and considering that contemporary experimental G the CODATA 2010 recommendation of $G_{\text{exp}} := [6.6738 \pm 0.0008] \times 10^{-11}$ [N m² kg⁻²], it is obtained that by assuming the validity of the DQG framework it can be used that $r_{\text{PC}} = \sqrt{\frac{I_{\text{SMP}} \hbar G}{16 c^3}}$; and hence it is possible to obtain an expression for gravitational constant G purely in terms of SMP parameters, the G_{SMP} , which for the contemporary universe agrees with G_{exp} :

$$G_{\text{SMP}} := \frac{2^{20/3} 3^2 \alpha^{2/9} c^3 \xi_{\text{baryon}}^{10}}{I_{\text{SMP}}^3 \hbar \xi_{ep}^8} = [6.6_{-0.7}^{+0.8}] \times 10^{-11} \text{ [N m}^2 \text{ kg}^{-2}] \approx G_{\text{exp}}, \quad (13)$$

where both c and \hbar are assumed to be invariant. Likewise, using the relation between G and Planck length, $l_{\text{P}} := \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}}$; it is possible to obtain a Planck length directly from the SMP QFs, the $l_{\text{P}_{\text{SMP}}}$, which is in agreement with the experimental Planck length $l_{\text{P}_{\text{exp}}} := \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G_{\text{exp}}}{c^3}}$, since

$$l_{\text{P}_{\text{SMP}}} := \frac{2^{10/3} 3 \alpha^{1/9} \xi_{\text{baryon}}^5}{I_{\text{SMP}}^{\frac{3}{2}} \xi_{ep}^4} = [1.61 \pm 0.1] \times 10^{-35} \text{ [m]} \approx l_{\text{P}_{\text{exp}}}. \quad (14)$$

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